

Mivick: Alert and monitoring system to cyclists and motorcyclists

Mivick: Sistema de alerta e monitoramento para ciclistas e motociclistas

Mivick: Sistema de vigilancia y alerta para ciclistas y motociclistas

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Abstract:

This project proposes the development of a monitoring system for the security of cyclists and motorcyclists on bike lanes and blue lanes. Using IoT technology and embedded sensors, such as accelerometers, gyroscopes, impact sensors, and distance sensors, the device can detect falls, minor collisions, and risk situations. The motivation stems from the high risk of accidents involving inattentive, reckless or alcohol-driving drivers, which makes these users more vulnerable. Our main objective is to offer a technological solution that increases protection, reduces incidents and promotes greater confidence in the use of these spaces. The research combines quantitative and qualitative approaches to identify the vital scenario of dangers and understand the user's needs. The system transmits immediate alerts via the mobile app. It is expected that the solution will increase road security, reduce accidents, and promote greater autonomy and confidence among cyclists and motorcyclists in urban areas.

Resumo:

Este trabalho propõe o desenvolvimento de um sistema de monitoramento voltado à segurança de ciclistas e motociclistas em ciclofaixas e faixas azuis. Utilizando tecnologia IoT e sensores embarcados, como acelerômetro, giroscópio, sensor de impacto e sensor de distância, o dispositivo é capaz de detectar quedas, colisões leves e situações de risco. A motivação decorre do elevado risco de acidentes envolvendo motoristas desatentos, desgovernados ou sob efeito de álcool, que tornam esses usuários mais vulneráveis. O objetivo central é oferecer uma solução tecnológica que aumente a proteção, reduza incidentes e promova maior confiança no uso desses espaços. A pesquisa combina abordagens qualitativas e quantitativas para identificar os principais cenários de perigo e compreender as necessidades dos usuários. O sistema transmite alertas imediatos via aplicativo móvel. Espera-se que a solução aumente a segurança viária, reduza o número de acidentes e promova maior autonomia e confiança para ciclistas e motociclistas no ambiente urbano.

Resumen:

Este trabajo propone el desarrollo de un sistema de monitorización dirigido a la seguridad de ciclistas y motociclistas en carriles bici y carril azul. Utilizando tecnología IoT y sensores integrados, como acelerómetro, giroscopio, sensor de impacto y sensor de distancia, el dispositivo es capaz de detectar caídas, colisiones leves y situaciones de riesgo. La motivación surge del alto riesgo de accidentes que involucran a conductores distraídos, fuera de control o bajo la influencia del alcohol, lo que hace que estos usuarios sean más vulnerables. El objetivo central es ofrecer una solución tecnológica que aumente la protección, reduzca las incidencias y promueva una mayor confianza en el uso de estos espacios. La investigación combina enfoques cualitativos y cuantitativos para identificar escenarios de peligros clave y comprender las necesidades de los usuarios. El sistema transmite alertas inmediatas a través de la aplicación móvil. Se espera que la solución aumente la seguridad vial, reduzca el número de accidentes y promueva una mayor autonomía y confianza de ciclistas y motociclistas en el entorno urbano.

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1. Introduction

The lack of traffic safety is evident, especially for cyclists and motorcyclists, who are its most vulnerable users. Even with cycle lanes and blue lanes in place, many drivers disregard them, exposing users to various risks. Cases of vehicle break-ins, often by drunk or inattentive drivers, result in serious accidents. In 2024, the city of São Paulo recorded 1,031 traffic deaths, 37% of which involved motorcyclists, according to data from Detran (2024).

Based on the problem presented, the objective of the project is to create a prototype of an IoT system integrated with devices and a mobile application capable of preventing accidents and alerting in the event of an emergency in traffic, where, with the use of sensors, it will trigger alerts in real time, contributing to the prevention of accidents and the protection of lives in traffic.

We hypothesize that the lack of safety and driver negligence have increased the number of accidents each year. The leading causes found were roads and cycle lanes in a state of abandonment, left in precarious conditions, or not even finished. This means that cyclists and motorcyclists end up using roads with heavy traffic and little monitoring for incidents of this type. Even though cyclists use cycle lanes and motorcyclists use the blue lane, lack of attention is also one of the most significant factors in accidents, caused, for example, by cell phone use in traffic, headphones, and the lack of signage on roads and highways.

Bearing these hypotheses in mind, one can observe the need to use technology to reduce the number of deaths and accidents in traffic, which led to the creation of this project, which aims to provide better safety for cyclists and motorcyclists, who, to date, only have basic safety equipment that puts the lives of both at risk, even with the recommended precautions.

The project's focus area is the metropolitan area of São Paulo, where drivers of large vehicles, cyclists, and motorcyclists use many roads, avenues, and streets. This public will be the focus during the system's creation.

To achieve the project's fundamental objectives, we asked: how can technology improve street safety and reduce the number of accidents involving cyclists and motorcyclists?

2. Theoretical Foundation

In this section, the head concepts, theories and studies that underpin the development of the Mivick project are presented. The aim is to contextualize themes related to the Internet of Things (IoT), road safety, and smart sensors, which support the device's proposal.

2.1. Traffic accidents involving cyclists and motorcyclists

Traffic accidents involving cyclists and motorcyclists are still one of the biggest reasons for traffic deaths (MINISTÉRIO DA SAÚDE, 2023). Brazilian legislation recognizes the vulnerability of these groups, but the lack of care, prudence, and proper infrastructure increases the risks faced by cyclists and motorcyclists (ABRMET 2023).

Traffic violence results in 76% of deaths among cyclists, pedestrians and motorcyclists (CNN, 2024) and can also cause physical injuries, psychological trauma and lasting social limitations. Therefore, as mentioned in the study by Bastos *et al.* (2018), it is necessary to invest in infrastructure and traffic safety, further to increase cyclists' visibility on public roads through technology. In this context, initiatives based on the Internet of Things (IoT) show promise for reducing risks and enabling the development of intelligent solutions to detect dangerous situations.

2.2. Internet of Things (IoT)

According to Monteiro and Santos (2020), IoT is a set of technologies that connect the physical and digital worlds, using sensors and embedded systems to monitor, control, and automate tasks remotely and intelligently.

IoT is characterized by the interconnection of physical devices with the internet, allowing them to send and receive data without direct human intervention (GODOI; ARAÚJO, 2020). This characteristic makes the technology especially suitable for vehicle safety applications, such as Mivick.

2.3. Python

For IoT programming, Python was used, a high-level programming language with a simple and straightforward syntax, which facilitates learning for beginners and at the same time offers advanced features for experienced programmers (SWARUP; PILLAI, 2018).

This language stands out for its ability to automate day-to-day tasks simply, even for non-programmers, helping to save time and effort (SWEIGART, 2016).

According to Ribeiro and Santos (2021), Python is the ideal language for beginners, as it combines simplicity with power, making it easier for people from different areas to learn programming.

Figure 1 – Python Example


```
1
2 matriz_numeros = [
3     [1,2,3],
4     [4,5,6],
5     [7,8,9],
6     [0],
7 ]
8
9 for linhas in matriz_numeros:
10     print("-----")
11
12     for colunas in linhas:
13         print(colunas)
14
15
```

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

2.4. Smart Sensors and Microcontrollers

The development of intelligent security systems depends on integrating microcontrollers and embedded sensors that collect, process, and transmit data. These components permit devices to analyze the environment and efficiently identify risk situations, an essential feature for the Mivick project.

The ESP32, as described by Morais (2023, p. 4-15), is a high-performance microcontroller that stands out for its versatility and wireless communication capabilities. It is ideal for IoT applications of remote monitoring and continuous communication between devices. (SOUZA, 2023, p. 6).

In Mivick, the ESP32 microcontroller integrates the MPU6050 (accelerometer and gyroscope), the SW-420 (impact sensor), and the HC-SR04 (distance sensor). The fusion of data from these sensors habilitates precise identification of abnormal movement, collisions, and falls.

2.5. React Native and EXPO

The Mivick system's mobile application was developed using React Native, a framework designed for mobile app development (Escudelario; Pinho, 2021, p. 2).

According to Escudelario and Pinho (2021, p. 15-25), Expo is a framework built on React Native that grants the development of mobile applications using only JavaScript, dispensing with tools such as Android Studio or Xcode.

Figure 2 - React Native example


```
1 import { View, Text, TextInput } from "react-native";
2 import React, { useState } from 'react';
3
4 export default function Index() {
5
6   const [nome, setNome] = useState("");
7   const [email, setEmail] = useState("");
8
9   return (
10     <View>
11
12       <Text>Bem vindo ao Aplicativo</Text>
13
14       <TextInput
15
16         onChangeText={setNome}
17         value={nome}
18         placeholder="Digite seu Nome no campo:"
19       />
20
21       <TextInput
22
23         onChangeText={setEmail}
24         value={email}
25         placeholder="Digite seu Email no campo:"
26       />
27
28     </View>
29   );
30 }
31
```

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

2.6. Database

For the database, the SQLite system was chosen, which is a database management system for the Android platform, storing data locally, that is, on the device itself, making it ideal for applications that require speed and offline operations (Comachio, 2011).

For Gomes (2022), SQLite is essential for the offline functionality of mobile applications, keeping the app functional even without a connection, securely storing structured data, and being multiplatform and widely supported.

Figure 3 – SQLite Example

```
1 import sqlite3
2
3 conexao = sqlite3.connect("meu_banco.db")
4
5 cursor = conexao.cursor()
6
7 cursor.execute("""
8 CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS usuarios (
9     id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY AUTOINCREMENT,
10     nome TEXT NOT NULL,
11     email TEXT UNIQUE NOT NULL
12 )
13 """)
14
15 cursor.execute("INSERT INTO usuarios (nome, email) VALUES (?, ?)",
16               ("Maria Silva", "maria@email.com"))
17 cursor.execute("INSERT INTO usuarios (nome, email) VALUES (?, ?)",
18               ("João Souza", "joao@email.com"))
19
20 conexao.commit()
21
22 cursor.execute("SELECT * FROM usuarios")
23 usuarios = cursor.fetchall()
24
25 print("Usuários cadastrados:")
26 for usuario in usuarios:
27     print(usuario)
28
29 conexao.close()
```

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

2.7. UML

For diagramming, we used UML, which, according to BOOCH (2006), is a standard language for structuring software projects. UML is just a language, and hence it is just one part of a software development method.

UML is a modeling language widely used in software engineering because it is versatile and applicable to different areas. It has become the international industry standard for representing systems in a clear and structured way (GUEDES, 2011).

3. Method

This chapter will outline the fundamental steps for designing the project, including the methodology, UML documentation, and the essential concepts for creating the system.

3.1. Development Methodology

The research method used falls within the quantitative tradition, which, according to Lakatos and Marconi (2003), uses statistical techniques to quantify information, employing numerical data and in-depth statistical analysis for a given subject. Quantitative research uses numerical data to produce analytical results.

Based on our research, we developed the project to address the high number of traffic accidents caused by violations of traffic laws, resulting in a high mortality rate. Aiming to alleviate the situation, this project was developed to focus exclusively on the individual's real-time safety.

3.2. System diagramming

For simplified documentation of our project, we use UML. According to Guedes (2011) UML is a visual language used to model software and systems, to start the structure of our project a simple use case diagram was created, focused on the functions with two actors, the client and the IoT, and the environment that would be the application that will mediate between these cases, maintaining a CRUD of contacts necessary for security and receiving the alert, establishing a connection with the device, sending information and photos to the application, explained simply and intuitively to show how the software works.

Figure 4 – Use case of the system

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

The use case documentation was designed based on the UML model, functional requirements, non-functional requirements, and business rules.

Below are the functional requirements of the system, which serve to represent a system functionality that interacts directly with the user:

- RF01: Detect sudden impacts with SW-420 sensor;
- RF02: Detect falls and sudden changes in inclination with MPU6050 gyroscope accelerometer;
- RF03: Measure distance to nearby objects with ultrasonic sensor;
- RF04: Send photo when an accident is detected;
- RF05: Notify emergency contacts via app, email or WhatsApp;
- RF06: Register critical events in the database;
- RF07: Act automatically if multiple sensors confirm a risk;
- RF08: Allow the configuration of emergency contacts via the app.
- RF09: Charge 18650 battery automatically via TP4056 when connected the external source;
- RF10: Supply 5V to ESP32-CAM using MT3608 from 3.5V battery;
- RF11: Present history and information collected from the device in the application;
- RF12: Edit users and contacts.

Next are the system's non-functional requirements, which represent characteristics requested by the user:

- RFN01: The sensors must work correctly even with vibrations.

- RFN02: The time between event detection and alert sending must be less than 5 seconds.
- RFN03: The device must operate for several hours in standby mode.
- RFN04: The system must continue operating even if one of the sensors fails.
- RFN05: The device must be light and small.
- RFN06: It should be easy to replace the device battery or recharge it.
- RFN07: Initial configuration via app must be simple;
- RFN08: The device must be water/splash resistant.
- RFN09: The app must be quick to send alerts.
- RFN10: The app experience should focus on simplicity and security.

The system also has business rules, which define rules that the system must follow to maintain the system's performance and functionality without compromising the user experience:

- It is necessary to register or log in to access the system.
- At least 1 contact must be registered in the app.
- The system does not send an alert when the battery charge is below 5%.
- The system only activates the camera if it is connected.
- Each device can only have up to 3 emergency contacts configured.
- The system goes into energy-saving mode after 60 hours of inactivity.
- It is not allowed to recharge the batteries while the system is operating at high load to avoid overheating.
- The minimum collision distance is 50cm if an object is detected, unless the system registers it as a near collision.

3.3. Mobile Application

Wireframes were developed for the project, a sketch to base the project on; within this sketch, the fonts and sizes were defined, along with the chosen color palette, in a way that conveys a feeling of security, simplicity, and objectivity.

Below is a brief explanation of the principal wireframes developed for the system's mobile application.

Figure 5 – Wireframe of the home variations

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

The wireframe home page can give us a good idea of the application and its functionalities, including connecting a device, registering contacts to receive alerts, and viewing the history of alerts sent by the device to the application. Furthermore, the entire application follows the same color palette and style as the components.

We used the React Native language to create our multiplatform project, creating reusable components and libraries of the framework itself, the components were divided and created with the respective names of each wireframe element, in total 12 components were used to assemble the base structure of the project, each component has its own folder that contains a file for export and the component's own styling, in addition to the folders that contain images and icons and page styling, for the backend node.js was used, connected and created a SQLite database to store information quickly and in a lighter way, to create this API and use it via URL, built from a software architecture model, separating the folders between connection to the database and the intermediate ones with the application.

To build the database, we drafted the relationships and tables we would use, and we opted for SQLite, a lightweight, simple-to-use, offline option.

3.4. Devices

The two devices were designed to be able to identify, alert and try to prevent an accident, using movement sensors, along with cameras, the device is exceptionally functional, connected via WI-FI,

the sensors capture the distance, movement and possible impact of the driver, when exceeding the speed limits the system captures a photo taken at the time of an alert, moreover to recording logs of what happened, such as the date and time of the event.

We also created a basic draft of the 3D model based on measurements of each component, resulting in a simple design with excellent durability in everyday use and almost no discomfort.

4. Results and Discussions

This chapter discusses the devices, the application, and their connection, as well as a brief discussion of the results we still intend to achieve.

4.1. Device Prototype

The image below demonstrates the crucial prototype of the device. In it, each sensor and each functionality were tested, so the essential working device emerged.

Figure 6 – Device Prototype

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

4.2. Mobile Application

The application, developed in React Native, primarily receives alerts, registers the contacts who will receive them in the event of an accident, and displays the sensor activation history. Below is a demonstration of the device connection pages, followed by the device settings page, where the user can turn on and off the device and its sensors, and the sensor alert history page.

Figure 7 – Connection with the device page

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

Figura 8 – Settings and history page

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

The demonstrated pages are a focus of our application. The user can control the connected devices, and the application and the devices share information, showing that the connection between them works.

Furthermore to these pages, the application also has contact pages, register and edit a contact, where the user can register and edit the contacts that will receive alerts in the event of an accident.

Figura 9 – Contact Pages

Source: Own Authorship (2025)

4.3. Conclusion

The system was created to offer more modern technology that really offers more security for cyclists and motorcyclists, and we were able to offer this, there are several improvements to be made in the project, such as strengthening the system database by making it operate with different databases in offline and online mode, improving equipment and latest technologies to be applied in the application, so far we have reached a stable point offering what we promised, modern and low-cost security with the development of the system in an impeccable way, however there are still improvements to be made in the project and not we can reach the audience in the desired way.

5. Final Considerations

Based on the research results, it is possible to conclude that cyclists and motorcyclists are particularly vulnerable to traffic accidents, which led to the creation of the Mivick system, which alerts and enhances safety for these users. As a result, we were clear on how we can use technology to help the public feel safer when carrying out simple actions, such as riding a bicycle or a motorbike. Our system can generate more alerts and, consequently, more attention from users and those around them, reducing the rate of accidents caused by inattention.

This solution can also reach more people because it is low-cost. The assembled devices, like the application, were made using technology that, despite somewhat complex functions, is affordable, making the solution cheaper while still delivering the expected results.

In short, an effective and low-cost solution was created that shows us the importance of thinking about users who are vulnerable, but are not always the focus of research and especially technological proposals that can help reduce traffic accidents and the mortality rate in Brazil, making this type of situation more neglected by society compared to other causes.

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